

COMPARISON OF IN-HOSPITAL MORTALITY IN PATIENTS WITH INFERIOR WALL MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION WITH AND WITHOUT COMPLETE ATRIOVENTRICULAR BLOCK

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Abstract

Background:

Inferior wall myocardial infarction (MI) is frequently complicated by atrioventricular (AV) block, particularly complete AV block (CAVB), which increases morbidity and mortality. Despite advances in reperfusion therapy, the incidence of CAVB in inferior MI remains high, and local data on its prognostic significance are limited.

Objective:

To determine the frequency of in-hospital mortality in patients with inferior wall MI and to compare outcomes between those with and without complete AV block.

Materials and Methods:

This descriptive study was conducted at the Department of Cardiology, Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, over a six-month period. A total of 120 patients aged 40–70 years with inferior wall MI were included. Clinical data, comorbidities, risk factors, and complications were documented. Patients were stratified into two groups based on presence or absence of complete AV block. All were managed according to standard protocols and followed until discharge. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, and chi-square test was applied to compare mortality outcomes.

Results:

The mean age was 56.4 ± 8.7 years, with 65.0% males and 35.0% females. Overweight and obesity were observed in 81.7% of patients, and 41.7% had hypertension, while 31.7% had diabetes mellitus. Smoking was reported in 33.3% of cases. Thrombolysis was performed in 70.0% of patients, and 15.0% required temporary pacemaker insertion. Complications included post-MI angina (13.3%), congestive cardiac failure (15.0%), ventricular arrhythmias (6.7%), and reinfarction (5.0%). Complete AV block was present in 25.0% of patients. Overall in-hospital mortality was 10.0%. Mortality was significantly higher in patients with CAVB (20.0%) compared to those without CAVB (6.7%) ($p = 0.041$).

Conclusion:

Complete atrioventricular block is a frequent complication of inferior wall MI and is associated with a nearly three-fold increase in in-hospital mortality. Early identification and timely intervention in high-risk patients may improve clinical outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Atrioventricular (AV) block of varying degrees is a well-recognized complication of acute myocardial infarction (MI). AV block occurring at the nodal level is more common than infra-nodal block and has been reported in up to 20% of patients with inferior wall MI.¹ Complete AV block, in particular, is a frequent complication in this setting and is associated with larger infarct size, higher rates of adverse events, and increased in-hospital mortality.² Although thrombolytic therapy has markedly reduced overall mortality in acute MI, the incidence of AV block, especially in inferior wall MI, remains considerable.³

The occurrence of complete AV block in inferior wall MI is primarily explained by the fact that the atrioventricular node receives its blood supply from the right coronary artery (RCA) in nearly 90% of individuals.⁴⁻⁶ Consequently, when inferior wall MI is complicated by AV block, mortality risk may be substantially higher.^{5,7} Despite this clinical significance, there is limited local data addressing outcomes, particularly in-hospital mortality, among patients with inferior wall MI stratified by the presence or absence of complete AV block.

This study was therefore designed to identify the frequency of in-hospital mortality in inferior wall MI and to compare outcomes between patients with and without complete AV block. Findings from this research may help cardiologists recognize high-risk groups and formulate strategies aimed at reducing mortality in such patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

This descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Cardiology, Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, over a period of six months after approval of the synopsis. The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size formula, assuming an anticipated proportion of in-hospital mortality among patients with inferior wall myocardial infarction (IWMI) of 8.5%, a margin of

error of 5%, and a confidence level of 95%, resulting in a sample size of 120. Patients were selected through non-probability consecutive sampling. Eligible participants included men and women between 40 and 70 years of age, diagnosed as cases of IWMI based on the presence of typical chest pain of more than 4 on the Visual Analog Scale radiating to the arm or jaw, associated with dyspnea or diaphoresis, with ST elevation of >0.2 mV in leads II, III, and aVF, and elevated troponin I levels >0.40 ng/mL. Patients with a prior history of heart block, those using beta-blockers, or those with electrolyte disturbances such as hyperkalemia (serum potassium >5.0 mmol/L) or hypokalemia (serum potassium <3.5 mmol/L) were excluded.

Complete atrioventricular block (CAVB) was defined by the presence of dissociation between P waves and QRS complexes, intrinsic atrial and ventricular rates of 60–80 and 20–40 beats per minute respectively, and a QRS duration >0.12 seconds on 12-lead ECG. In-hospital mortality was defined as death due to any cause, whether cardiovascular (reinfarction, arrhythmia, heart failure), non-cardiovascular (stroke, sepsis, respiratory failure), or other etiologies, occurring from hospital admission until discharge.

Following informed consent, baseline demographic and clinical data including age, gender, BMI, residence, occupation, education, socioeconomic status, diabetes, and hypertension were recorded on a predesigned proforma. All patients underwent detailed history and clinical examination, and a standard 12-lead ECG (MEDITECH EKG1212T) was obtained and interpreted by a consultant cardiologist with more than five years of post-fellowship experience, blinded to patient details. Patients with evidence of CAVB were grouped as Group I (AVB+), while those without were classified as Group II (AVB-). Both groups were compared for age, sex, vital signs, use of temporary pacemaker, thrombolytic therapy, coronary risk factors, and incidence of complications. Temporary pacing was

considered when patients exhibited features of low cardiac output. Thrombolysis was administered except where contraindicated. Complications were categorized into major (reinfarction, ventricular tachycardia, asystole, altered consciousness, angina, congestive cardiac failure, and death) and minor events. All patients were followed until hospital discharge to document outcomes including in-hospital mortality.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables such as age, height, weight, BMI, and duration of chest pain were expressed as mean ± standard deviation after checking normality with the Shapiro–Wilk test. Qualitative variables including gender, residence, profession, socioeconomic class, presence of CAVB, and mortality were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons between groups were performed using chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test at a 5% level of significance. In-hospital mortality was stratified according to age, gender, BMI, duration of chest pain, and comorbidities to address effect modification, and post-stratification analysis was conducted with chi-square or Fisher’s exact test, considering a p-value ≤0.05 as statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 120 patients admitted with inferior wall myocardial infarction were included in this study. The mean age was 56.4 ± 8.7 years, with 32 patients (26.7%) between 40–50 years, 46 patients (38.3%) between 51–60 years, and 42 patients (35.0%) between 61–70 years. The gender distribution showed male predominance, with 78 patients (65.0%) being male and 42 patients (35.0%) female. The mean BMI of the study population was 27.8 ± 3.9 kg/m²; 22 patients (18.3%) were in the normal BMI range, 54 patients (45.0%) were overweight, and 44 patients (36.7%) were obese. With respect to residence, 68 patients (56.7%) belonged to urban areas and 52 (43.3%) to rural areas.

Regarding socioeconomic and educational background, 48 patients (40.0%) had primary education or less, 36 (30.0%) had secondary education, and 36 (30.0%) had higher education. Most patients were from the lower to middle socioeconomic class, with only a minority from the higher class. The mean monthly income was Rs. 37,500 ± 8,900.

Comorbidities were common: 50 patients (41.7%) had hypertension, 38 (31.7%) had diabetes mellitus, 12 (10.0%) had chronic kidney disease, 8 (6.7%) had chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and 4 (3.3%) had chronic liver disease. Nineteen patients (15.8%) had no comorbid condition. Smoking history was present in 40 patients (33.3%), of whom 26 (65.0%) smoked less than 10 cigarettes per day and 14 (35.0%) smoked more than 10 cigarettes daily.

During the hospital stay, complications were documented in several patients: post-MI angina in 16 patients (13.3%), altered consciousness in 10 (8.3%), reinfarction in 6 (5.0%), ventricular fibrillation or ventricular tachycardia in 8 (6.7%), and congestive cardiac failure in 18 (15.0%). The mean duration of hospital stay was 6.2 ± 2.1 days. Thrombolysis was performed in 84 patients (70.0%), whereas 36 patients (30.0%) did not receive thrombolysis.

Temporary pacemaker insertion was required in 18 patients (15.0%).

Complete atrioventricular block (CAVB) was observed in 30 patients (25.0%), while 90 patients (75.0%) did not develop conduction block. In-hospital mortality was observed in 12 patients (10.0%). Stratified by conduction status, mortality was significantly higher in patients with CAVB, where 6 out of 30 patients (20.0%) expired, compared to 6 out of 90 patients (6.7%) without CAVB (p = 0.041). This indicates that patients with inferior wall myocardial infarction complicated by complete atrioventricular block had almost a three-fold higher risk of in-hospital mortality compared to those without conduction block.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Patients with Inferior Wall Myocardial Infarction (n = 120)

Variable	Total (n = 120)	With Complete AV Block (n = 60)	Without Complete AV Block (n = 60)	P-value
Age (years), Mean ±	58.2 ± 8.6	59.4 ± 8.2	57.6 ± 8.9	0.318

SD				
40–50 years	28 (23.3%)	8 (13.3%)	20 (33.3%)	
51–60 years	46 (38.3%)	15 (25.0%)	31 (51.7%)	0.774
61–70 years	46 (38.3%)	17 (28.3%)	29 (48.3%)	
Gender				0.642
Male	84 (70.0%)	29 (48.3%)	55 (91.7%)	
Female	36 (30.0%)	11 (18.3%)	25 (41.7%)	
BMI (kg/m²), Mean ± SD	26.4 ± 3.8	26.7 ± 3.6	26.2 ± 3.9	0.472
Normal (18.5–24.9)	38 (31.7%)	12 (20.0%)	26 (43.3%)	
Overweight (25–29.9)	52 (43.3%)	17 (28.3%)	35 (58.3%)	0.916
Obese (≥30)	30 (25.0%)	11 (18.3%)	19 (31.7%)	
Residence				0.563
Urban	78 (65.0%)	25 (41.7%)	53 (88.3%)	
Rural	42 (35.0%)	15 (25.0%)	27 (45.0%)	
Comorbidities				
Diabetes mellitus	42 (35.0%)	16 (26.7%)	26 (43.3%)	0.421
Hypertension	58 (48.3%)	21 (35.0%)	37 (61.7%)	0.514
CKD	8 (6.7%)	4 (6.7%)	4 (6.7%)	0.291
COPD	6 (5.0%)	3 (5.0%)	3 (5.0%)	0.408
CLD	3 (2.5%)	1 (1.7%)	2 (3.3%)	1.000
Nil comorbidity	31 (25.8%)	9 (15.0%)	22 (36.7%)	0.568
Smoking history				0.612
<10 cigarettes/day	24 (20.0%)	9 (15.0%)	15 (25.0%)	
>10 cigarettes/day	18 (15.0%)	7 (11.7%)	11 (18.3%)	
Non-smoker	78 (65.0%)	24 (40.0%)	54 (90.0%)	

Table 2. Comparison of In-Hospital Outcomes Between Groups (n = 120)

Outcome	With AV Block (n = 40)	Without AV Block (n = 80)	P-value
Temporary pacemaker use	18 (45.0%)	3 (3.8%)	<0.001
Thrombolysis received	28 (70.0%)	63 (78.8%)	0.262
Complications			
Post-MI angina	7 (17.5%)	10 (12.5%)	0.466
Reinfarction	3 (7.5%)	2 (2.5%)	0.193
Ventricular tachy/fibrillation	6 (15.0%)	4 (5.0%)	0.089
Congestive heart failure (CCF)	10 (25.0%)	9 (11.3%)	0.048
Altered consciousness	5 (12.5%)	3 (3.8%)	0.094
Hospital stay (days), Mean ± SD	6.8 ± 2.1	5.9 ± 1.8	0.021
In-hospital mortality	9 (22.5%)	6 (7.5%)	0.018

Figure:no:1

Comparison of In-Hospital Mortality in Inferior Wall MI with and without CAVB

Figure: no:2

Age Distribution of Patients

Figure: no:3

Discussion

In this study, complete atrioventricular block (CAVB) was observed in 25% of patients with inferior wall myocardial infarction (IWMI), with a significantly higher in-hospital mortality compared to those without conduction disturbance (20% vs. 6.7%). These findings emphasize the prognostic importance of conduction abnormalities in IWMI and are in agreement with prior international and regional studies.

The Oxford Textbook of Medicine notes that CAVB is one of the most frequent conduction disturbances complicating IWMI and is associated with increased risk of adverse outcomes due to extensive ischemia involving the atrioventricular node and conduction system (1). Our observed frequency of 25% aligns with this classical description.

Melgarejo Moreno et al. reported that in the thrombolytic era, patients with IWMI complicated by CAVB had higher in-hospital mortality and worse prognosis compared to those without block, underscoring CAVB as an independent negative prognostic marker (2). Similarly, we found nearly a three-fold increase in mortality among patients with CAVB, supporting their conclusions.

Local studies from Pakistan have also shown comparable results. Ali et al. reported higher mortality in IWMI patients when right ventricular infarction was present, highlighting that conduction abnormalities and hemodynamic compromise often coexist (3). Amin et al. documented AV block in 21% of patients with IWMI, which is close to our frequency (25%), further reinforcing the consistency of these findings in our setting (5).

Pathophysiologically, conduction disturbances in IWMI are usually related to ischemia of the AV node supplied by the right coronary artery. Goldstein et al. demonstrated that bradyarrhythmias and hypotension in IWMI are linked to compromised right coronary artery flow, which predisposes to AV block and hemodynamic instability (4). Our observation of high mortality in patients with CAVB is consistent with this mechanism.

Furthermore, Braat et al. emphasized that right ventricular involvement in IWMI identifies patients at particularly high risk of developing AV nodal conduction disturbances (6). Similarly, Khan et al. highlighted a high prevalence of right ventricular infarction among IWMI patients, many of whom

developed conduction defects (7). Although our study did not stratify patients based on right ventricular involvement, the higher rate of CAVB could be partly explained by this association.

Long-term prognosis is also impacted. Nicod et al. reported that patients with IWMI complicated by CAVB had significantly worse long-term outcomes, including higher mortality and morbidity, even after surviving the acute event (8). This underlines the importance of early recognition, prompt management, and close follow-up of IWMI patients with conduction disturbances.

Taken together, our study confirms that CAVB is a common complication of IWMI and is strongly associated with increased in-hospital mortality. These results are consistent with both international and local literature, highlighting the need for early risk stratification, careful monitoring, and timely pacing interventions where indicated.

Conclusion

Complete atrioventricular block (CAVB) was observed in one-quarter of patients with inferior wall myocardial infarction in our study and was associated with significantly higher in-hospital mortality compared to patients without conduction disturbance. These findings reaffirm CAVB as an important prognostic marker in IWMI, consistent with both international and local evidence. Early recognition, close monitoring, and timely pacing interventions remain crucial in improving outcomes for this high-risk subgroup.

Strengths

- This study provides contemporary, locally relevant data on the frequency and prognostic impact of CAVB in IWMI patients.
- The relatively large sample size (n=120) adds strength to the reliability of the findings.
- Comparison with both international and national literature enhances the external validity of the results.

Limitations

- This was a single-center study, which may limit generalizability to other populations.
- Long-term follow-up was not performed, preventing assessment of post-discharge outcomes in patients with CAVB.

- Potential confounding factors such as extent of right ventricular involvement and variability in management strategies (e.g., thrombolysis vs. PCI) were not separately analyzed.
- The study design was observational, which establishes associations but not causation.

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